

IMPLEMENTING TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES IN THE JORDANIAN TELECOMMUNICATIONS SECTOR: BALANCING QUALITY AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

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Abstract

This study investigated the implementation of quality management principles—specifically Management Commitment (Leadership), Customer and Employee Importance, Standing of Facts, Employee Full Participation, and Continuous Improvement (KAIZEN)—within the telecommunications sector in Jordan. The research was conducted via a questionnaire distributed to 267 employees across telecommunications companies, representing a response rate of 77% from an original pool of 800 employees. Findings indicated high levels of application for Management Commitment (3.82), Customer Importance (3.87), and Continuous Improvement (KAIZEN) (3.92). In contrast, the dimensions of Standing of Facts (3.64) and Employee Full Participation (3.64) were found to be at a moderate level, the balance between applying total quality management principles and complying with the sector's legal regulations is a key focus discussed in the study. The telecommunications sector in Jordan operates within a strict legal framework established by the Telecommunications Regulatory Commission (TRC), which enforces laws related to consumer protection, data privacy, licensing, and service quality. Based on these results, the study recommends that Jordanian telecommunications companies enhance awareness of total quality management principles and ensure that continuous improvement is integrated as a core management practice, driven by senior management commitment.

Keywords: Total Quality Management, Quality, Quality Principles, Jordanian Telecommunication Sector, (Zain, Orange, and Umniah), Legal Compliance, Jordanian, Regulatory Framework, Consumer Protection.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current century faces significant challenges for organizations, both quantitatively and qualitatively (Almaiah et al., 2022a; Alshirah et al., 2020; Daviy, 2023). Increased standards have sparked academic discussions around integrated management systems, particularly in the 1990s (Barbosa et al., 2022).

"Total Quality Management (TQM) is considered as a fundamental aspect that enhances the competitiveness of the organization, influenced by principles such as management

commitment (leadership). This entails the responsibility of top management to educate and train employees on the effective use of information systems" (Almajali et al., 2022). Furthermore, the importance of both customers and employees has been emphasized as another principle, as research indicates that the implementation of new management standards based on quality principles enhances collective customer loyalty (Lutfi et al., 2024).

Regarding the position of facts and full participation of employees, it is necessary to support the right to self-defense, as violations can lead to the invalidation of disciplinary procedures (Alhasan & Awaisheh, 2024).

The previous study showed the right to full participation of employees, which is one of the important principles in total quality management. The study (Arsić et al., 2012) showed that customer satisfaction is linked to employee satisfaction, which is reflected in the participation of all members of the company.

There has been an increasing interest in the field of continuous improvement over the past thirty years (Sanchez, L., & Blanco, B. 2014) B) as the principle of continuous improvement (KAIZEN) is considered a vital tool to promote continuous improvements in practices (Sahmi & El Abbadi, 2024). The implementation of continuous improvement systems (CI) is also one of the strategies used to achieve operational excellence in companies (Lleo et al., 2017).

"This study specifically examines the implementation of TQM in Jordan's telecommunications sector, focusing on its principles where customer satisfaction is paramount. The telecommunications sector, notable for direct customer feedback, illustrates this relationship, as past research has primarily assessed customers' perceptions of service quality "(Doherty et al., 2015), There are also other studies that support this idea (Al-Muani, L., et al., 2024).

The main objective of Total Quality Management (TQM) is to create and transfer more efficient and higher-quality services by fostering cooperation among organizational members (Alweteed, N., 2018). "The Jordanian Telecommunications Sector exemplifies success in meeting competitive elements in the international telecommunications market, attributed to a combination of effective policies, a qualified infrastructure, and a skilled workforce. Additionally, Information and Communication Technology plays a crucial role in driving economic growth" (Kanaan, R. K et al., 2020).

Jordan has been a pioneer among Arab nations in liberalizing its telecommunications market, updating 75% of its laws related to communications and information technology. Since 2002, the sector has consistently ranked among the top three for foreign direct investment, with revenues for communications and information technology increasing from an estimated \$450 million in 2000 to \$1 billion by 2005, maintaining similar growth rates into 2010 (<http://www.jordaninvestment.com>). This website was visited on 1/1/2025.

Understanding and implementing TQM is vital for the survival of local and international industries (Khan, J. H., 2003). Gronstedt's research (Gronstedt, A., 1996), involving eight telecom companies, emphasizes the significance of supporting TQM processes, such as teamwork, documentation, and departmental integration.

Organizations with effective knowledge management environments enable employees to enhance their productivity and competitiveness (Abbas, J., & Sağsan, M., 2019). Therefore, the application of TQM principles in the Jordanian telecommunications sector is crucial for fostering success and sustainability, and this study aims to assess the extent of these principles' application within the sector.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The telecommunications sector is one of the most vital and a dynamic sector in Jordan, as it actively participates in various other sectors. Despite the wealth of research on quality and its principles, studies specifically focusing on the application of quality principles within the telecommunications sector are relatively scarce. This gap in the literature underscores the significance of examining this important service sector, making the exploration of quality application in telecommunications a particularly crucial topic for further investigation.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

This study aims to establish a theoretical framework for the application of Total Quality Management (TQM) principles in the Jordanian telecommunications sector and to assess its capability to address external influences.

To achieve this, the study seeks to answer the central question regarding the application of TQM principles within the sector.

The following objectives have been formulated:

- Recognize the level of management commitment (leadership) implementation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Identify the significance of customers and employees in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Assess the application of the standing of facts in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Evaluate the level of continuous improvement (KAIZEN) application in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Determine the level of employee full participation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.

1.4 Research Importance

The significance of this study lies in determining the extent to which the principles of Total Quality Management (TQM) are applied in the Jordanian telecommunications sector and how this application interacts with various foundational concepts of TQM:

- Identify the level of management commitment (leadership) implementation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Determine the significance of customer and employee participation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Assess the application of the standing of facts in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Evaluate the level of continuous improvement (KAIZEN) implementation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- Examine the degree of employee full participation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector.

The researcher is motivated to study the Jordanian telecommunications sector due to their specialization and belief in its potential for future development and impact on other sectors. The application of TQM principles is essential for enhancing competitiveness, improving service quality, and establishing a strong position within the sector. This study seeks to enrich the literature by investigating how TQM principles can be applied in this vital sector, offering a modern perspective on TQM philosophy in the Jordanian context.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The study will include identifying the principles of TQM applied in the Jordanian telecommunications sector, represented by three main companies: Zain, Orange and Umniah, where the study population consists of workers in these three companies in various job positions (senior management, middle management, and the rest of the employees).

1.6 Methodology Of The Study

This research aims to investigate the application of Total Quality Management (TQM) principles in the Jordanian telecommunications sector. To achieve the study's objectives and obtain final results, two scientific research approaches will be employed:

- The analytical descriptive approach, which will explore essential literature on the history of TQM and the Jordanian telecommunications sector.
- The field research methodology, utilizing a survey/sampling strategy to collect data from the target community.

The study will utilize a questionnaire developed based on relevant literature and input from subject matter experts. The final phase will involve analyzing the results and engaging in discussions.

Data collected will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools, specifically employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). This analysis aims to derive accurate statistics to inform decisions and present results in a clear and actionable format for administrative purposes. Various statistical methods will be used, including:

- Reliability Test (Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient).
- Descriptive Statistics.
- Relative Importance Index.
- One-way ANOVA.

At the conclusion of the study, findings will be summarized, and conclusions and recommendations will be provided. This phase will include identifying potential issues based on the results and proposing applicable solutions.

1.7 Study limitations include

- Spatial limitation: this study will be limited to the three Jordanian telecom companies: Zain and Orange and Uamnia.
- Time study.
- Target groups: senior management, middle management and lower management.

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The researcher classified the studies on the subject into three groups:

- Previous Studies concerned with (TQM).
- Previous Studies concerned with Telecommunication sector in Jordan.
- Previous Studies concerned with (TQM) and Telecommunication sector in Jordan.

(1) Previous Studies concerned with TQM:

Hildebrandt, Kristensen, Kanji, and Dahlgaard, (1991) Total Quality Management (TQM) is seen as the result of accumulated experiences, observable in contexts with measurable historical data. It marks a shift towards a management-focused cultural approach, rooted in collective improvement theories rather than humanities theories of societal evolution. This perspective allows for the integration of learning theories to enhance corporate culture and suggests that combining knowledge from various fields can deepen the understanding of complex phenomena.

(Dale & Cooper, 1994) This study highlights the increasing importance of management in local and global economies, particularly with the service industry's growing contribution to GDP over the past twenty years. Key TQM practices that influence this growth include management commitment and leadership, customer focus, supplier relationships, quality design, employee empowerment, benchmarking, statistical process control, and training.

Mehra, S., & Ranganathan, S. (2008) TQM is recognized as a key approach for achieving and sustaining competitive advantage. This study supports the notion that TQM implementation is linked to performance quality and influenced by various behavioral factors, including senior management leadership, customer focus, human resource focus, and quality emphasis. Additionally, TQM tools and techniques such as organizational planning, process focus, and information analysis are crucial for successful TQM implementation.

Alnidawy, A. A. B. (2015) this study examines the critical role of human resources in achieving organizational goals, emphasizing the significant impact of managers' engagement with employees. Employees significantly influence the organization's image, and their feelings and involvement affect job satisfaction and the implementation of TQM. The research targeted 300 workers to assess how the ability to understand individuals deeply influences their job satisfaction. Statistical analysis of the collected data revealed a strong positive correlation between this understanding and job satisfaction within the organization. The study concludes with several recommendations based on its findings.

Douglas, T. J., & Judge Jr, W. Q. (2001) the authors investigated the relationship between the adoption of TQM practices and the competitive advantages gained by organizations, finding strong support for this connection. Additionally, their data indicated that organizational structure mediates the effectiveness of TQM implementation. Specifically, two measures of organizational structure, labeled 'Control' and 'Explore,' demonstrated both independent and interdependent effects on the financial performance of firms implementing TQM programs.

Georgiev and Ohtaki, (2019) the events of this study revolve around Under these tension's gatherings, quality and the management of value is considered by standards in various enterprises as one of the fundamental elements for accomplishing competitiveness.

Durana, P., Kral, P., Stehel, V., Lazaroiu, G., & Sroka, (2019) the events of this study revolve around reiterate that quality culture plays a critical role in TQM and suitable quality makes the board programs more powerful, industry (4.0) can be perceived as an extraordinary chance for the turn of events and improvement of seriousness, albeit the condition of arrangements for its execution fluctuates generally relying upon nation, area, or even a singular organization.

(2) Previous Studies concerned with Telecommunication sector in Jordan.

Khashman, A. M., & Al-Ryalat, H. A. (2015). This paper investigates the impact of electronic human resource management (e-HRM) practices—such as e-recruitment, e-

selection, e-training, e-performance appraisal, e-communications, and e-compensation—on operational performance in the Jordanian telecommunications sector, specifically among Zain, Orange, and Umniah. The study targeted employees in supervisory positions and used a descriptive analytical method with a stratified random sample of 178 individuals for data collection. A questionnaire was administered, and data were analyzed using SPSS software. The findings revealed a positive and statistically significant effect of e-HRM dimensions on operational performance, focusing on time, cost, service quality, and flexibility.

Khashman, A. M., & Al-Ryalat, H. A. (2015). This study examines the influence of customer relationship management systems (CRMS) on the performance of telecommunications companies in Jordan. A conceptual model was developed to establish the link between CRMS and performance, utilizing a self-administered questionnaire for data collection. Out of 300 distributed questionnaires to customer service employees, 140 valid responses were analyzed. The research applied quantitative methods, including descriptive analysis, regression models, and hypothesis testing. The results reveal a significant impact of CRMS dimensions—system quality, information quality, system usage, and user satisfaction—on company performance. Additionally, the study provides practical recommendations for implementing CRMS to improve organizational performance in the telecommunications sector.

(3) Previous Studies concerned with TQM (TQM) and Telecommunication sector in Jordan together.

Haddad, M. R. (2021), The study finds that Total Quality Management (TQM) sub-variables and dimensions of strategic agility are effectively implemented in Jordanian telecommunications companies, demonstrating a strong correlation between them. Three TQM sub-variables—process management, human resource management, and leadership—significantly influence strategic agility, with process management having the greatest impact. In contrast, customer focus does not significantly affect the strategic agility of these companies.

Al-Zyoud, M. F., Al-Mu'ani, L. A., Alsoud, M., & Alsoud, A. (2021). The study examined the role of Total Quality Marketing (TQM) in enhancing the effectiveness of e-marketing within the Jordanian telecommunications sector. TQM encompassed variables such as service quality, market orientation, and a customer-centric approach.

A quantitative methodology was employed, utilizing a survey distributed to 18 project supervisors in Jordanian telecommunications companies (Zain, Umniah, and Orange).

The findings indicated that TQM positively influences the efficacy and productivity of electronic marketing strategies, particularly in social marketing and the electronic display department.

3. STUDY METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

The study design serves as the conceptual framework guiding research, functioning as a blueprint for data acquisition, measurement, and analysis (Kothari, 2004). Selecting the appropriate study design is a crucial step in determining the research methodology (Omair, 2015). To achieve the objectives of this study, a descriptive and analytical research design was employed, which included a theoretical literature review, development of a study instrument, and collection of quantitative data from the sample. This descriptive design aimed to provide clear descriptions and deducible conclusions regarding the influence of TQM principles implementation in the Jordanian telecommunications sector. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized; primary data were collected directly from respondents, while secondary data were sourced from engineering articles, journals, working papers, theses, and the websites of the Jordanian telecommunications sector. An analytical design was implemented to derive the study results.

3.2 Target Population

Target population refers to all elements that satisfy the specified criteria for a research study, which element may be an individual, a house this research was conducted in the Jordanian telecommunication sector as one of the most competitive sectors in Jordan (Abuhashesh et al., 2019a). The population of this study consists of all employees at all managerial levels working in the three major telecommunication companies operating in Jordan (Orange, Zain, Umniah) (Kanaan, R. K et al., 2020). The total number of workers was 800 in the center of the main three telecommunication companies, according to the human resources department of the ministry of information and communications technology <https://portal.jordan.gov.jo>, the website was visited on 1/1/2025 and respondents were selected based on their familiarity with the topic of the study and willingness to participate in the survey.

3.3 Sampling Techniques

Within the informant sample, the quality of the literature, the richness of the data acquired, and the procedures undertaken ensure the credibility (Alexander & Varley, 2025). Sampling techniques are frequently applied in research investigations to provide more precise estimates at minimal cost and in less time (Singh & Masuku, 2014).

3.3.1 Sample Size of the Study

In applied statistics research problems, the selection of sampling techniques and determination of sample size is crucial for drawing accurate conclusions (Singh & Masuku, 2014). A simple random sampling method was utilized to identify the sample size; this technique means that every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected and included in the sample (Taherdoost, 2016), the sample size was

calculated based on the target employees in the departments of the Jordanian telecommunication sector identified using Yamane's (1967) formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \quad (1)$$

Where;

n: The sample Size

N: The population size

e: margin of error (5% and CI is 95%).

$$N = \frac{800}{1 + 800(0.05)^2} = \frac{800}{3} = 267 \text{ workers from the telecommunication sector.}$$

The sample comprised 267 employees who were randomly selected from the ministry of information and communications Technology to fill out the study questionnaire, the survey was made using a Google Drive form and sent out through email (see Appendix for details), the number of distributed questionnaires was 267, and the number of questionnaires that were retrieved was 206, so the response rate was 77% and this percentage is from the responses are acceptable for statistical analysis (Lutfi et al., 2022b; Alqudah, Amran & Hassan, 2019a)., the following Table (1) shows the distribution of the study sample according to their demographic variables.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants (n=206)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentages
Years of Experience		
(5- less than 10) Years	98	47.6%
(10- less than 20) year	66	32%
(20- less than 30) year	42	20.4%
Educational Level		
Diploma	30	15%
Bachelor	130	63.1%
Postgraduate	46	22.3%
Job Site		
Senior management	32	15.5%
Middle management	40	19.4%
Employee	134	65%
Functional section		
Financial management	24	11.7%
Contact management	16	7.8%
Strategic management	31	15%
Human Resource Management	56	27.2%
Customer management	28	13.6%
Sales Administration	6	2.9%
Network management	3	1.5%
Marketing Management	9	4.4%
Information Systems Management	33	16%

As can be shown in Table (1), the total number of employees who responded to the study was 206, and the majority of participants (47.6%) had experienced (5- less than 10 years) in the Jordanian Telecommunication sector, regarding the educational level, the majority of employees had a bachelor's degree (63.1%) followed by those who had a postgraduate (22.3%).

According to the functional section, the majority of respondents were employees from human resources (27.2%), followed by information systems management (16%), and then strategic management (15%), As a result, the demographic information about the respondents underscores their substantial knowledge and experience, making them well-suited to partake in the survey and provide reliable data for this study (Al Qudah, Osman & Al Qudah, 2014; Alrfaiet al., 2023; Alghadi et al., 2023; Alqudah, Amran & Hassan,2019b).

3.4 Study Tool

The questionnaire was used as a research tool to investigate the study's objectives and problem statement. It featured closed-ended questions on a Five Likert Scale ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," ultimately comprising 37 items after validating its reliability.

The development of the questionnaire involved the following steps:

- Identifying the questionnaire's objectives based on the study statement and determining the necessary data to meet these goals.
- Carefully selecting the questionnaire items to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- Distributing the validated questionnaire to the sample members.
- Collecting the completed questionnaires for data analysis.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections: the first gathered demographic information about respondents, while the second focused on the study's subject, addressing five key principles: Management Commitment (Leadership), Importance of Customer and Employee, Standing of Facts, Employee Full Participation, and Continuous Improvement (KAISEN).

4. THE RESULTS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This part of study provides a comprehensive presentation of the study results in light of its hypotheses, which sought to identify the extent of implementation of principles of TQM in improving the companies of the Jordanian telecommunications sector.

In addition, it contains a discussion of the study results and their interpretation in accordance with the order of its hypotheses.

4.1 Analysis of Study Questions

This section presents the analysis of descriptive statistics relevant to the study's variables, including arithmetic means, standard deviations, and maximum and minimum values. Standard deviation serves as a measure of sample dispersion, while arithmetic means indicate central tendency.

Descriptive statistics are utilized to assess the level of TQM principles implementation—namely Management Commitment (Leadership), Importance of Customer and Employee, Standing of Facts, Employee Full Participation, and Continuous Improvement (KAISEN)—in Jordanian telecommunications companies.

The analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 as the research tool.

4.1.1 First Question: What are the most important principles of TQM implemented in the Jordanian telecommunications sector?

To answer this question, descriptive statistics and a relative importance index were used to assess the degree of implementation of the principles of TQM in the Jordanian telecommunications sector according to the perceptions of the respondents; the results are shown in table (2) below.

Table 2: Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and relative importance index about the implementing degree of TQM principles

NO.	Principle	Min – Max	Mean	Std. D	RII	Level	Rank
1.	Management Commitment	2.80 – 4.80	3.82	0.43	.76	M-H	3
2.	Importance of customers and employees	1.82 – 5	3.87	0.67	.77	M-H	2
3.	Standing of Facts	1.40 – 5	3.62	0.75	.72	M-H	5
4.	Full participation	2.20 – 5	3.64	0.63	.73	M-H	4
5.	Continuous Improvement	1.50 – 5	3.92	0.76	.79	M-H	1
	The tool as a whole	2.95 – 4.59	3.73	0.33			

*Abbreviations: Min: Minimum value on the Likert scale; Max: Maximum on the Likert scale; SD: Standard Deviation; RII: Relative Importance Index.

It is clear from Table (2) that the arithmetic means of the respondents' perceptions about the degree of implementation of the TQM principles ranged from 3.62 to 3.92, with a standard deviation that ranged from 0.43 to 0.76. The principle of continuous improvement came in the first rank with an arithmetic mean (M=3.92), standard deviation (SD=0.76), and relative importance index (RII=0.79). The principle of the standing of facts came in the last rank with an arithmetic mean (M=3.62), standard deviation (SD=0.75), and relative importance index (RII=0.72). Based on the relative importance index (RII) analysis in figure (1) for the application of the TQM principles, continuous improvement was ranked first from the perspective of participants with less than ten years of experience with an RII value of (0.80), individuals with post-graduate degrees with an RII value was (0.81), and employees with an RII value was (0.81).

Figure 1: RII values to rank the TQM principles according to A: years of experience, B: educational level, and C: Job Site

This result is attributable to the fact that employees in Jordanian telecommunications firms recognize the significance of implementing the principles of TQM.

This result agreed with a study by (Alaoun & Sharabati 2018) that showed the principle of continuous improvement had a high degree of agreement from the viewpoint of the participants in Qatar Telecommunication companies, and a study by (Alawag et al, 2023) that showed the principle of continuous improvement is the most important factor.

4.1.2 Second Question: What are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample towards the implementation of Total Quality Management Principles in the Jordanian telecommunications sector companies due to the variables of years of experience, job site, and educational level?

To answer this question, Descriptive statistics of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable. The results are shown below.

Years of Experience:

Calculations of arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable years of experience are shown in Table (3).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable years of experience

Principle	Levels of experience years	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
A commitment of management	5 - less than 10 years	98	3.88	0.42
	10 - less than 20 years	66	3.76	0.43
	20-above 30 years	42	3.78	0.45
	Total	206	3.82	0.43
Importance of customers and employees	5 - less than 10 years	98	3.98	0.64
	10 - less than 20 years	66	3.71	0.64
	20-above 30 years	42	3.85	0.76
	Total	206	3.87	0.67
Standing of facts	5 - less than 10 years	98	3.62	0.75
	10 - less than 20 years	66	3.62	0.74
	20-above 30 years	42	3.62	0.80
	Total	206	3.62	0.75
Full Participation	5 - less than 10 years	98	3.69	0.62
	10 - less than 20 years	66	3.68	0.61
	20-above 30 years	42	3.48	0.67
	Total	206	3.64	0.63
Continuous Improvement	5 - less than 10 years	98	3.90	0.76
	10 - less than 20 years	66	3.88	0.73
	20 - above 30 years	42	4.00	0.81
	Total	206	3.91	0.76

From the results in Table (3), there were apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable years of experience.

Educational Level

Calculations of arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable years of experience are shown in Table (4).

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable educational level

Principle	Levels of educational qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
A commitment of management	Diploma	30	3.80	0.46
	Bachelor	130	3.84	0.43
	Post-graduate	46	3.79	0.41
	Total	206	3.82	0.43
Importance of customers and employees	Diploma	30	3.44	0.62
	Bachelor	130	3.91	0.66
	Post-graduate	46	4.04	0.65
	Total	206	3.87	0.67
Standing of facts	Diploma	30	3.92	0.74
	Bachelor	130	3.56	0.75
	Post-graduate	46	3.58	0.78
	Total	206	3.61	0.76
Full Participation	Diploma	30	3.86	0.54
	Bachelor	130	3.63	0.62
	Post-graduate	46	3.57	0.72
	Total	206	3.65	0.63
Continuous Improvement	Diploma	30	3.98	0.88
	Bachelor	130	3.91	0.72
	Post-graduate	46	3.87	0.78
	Total	206	3.92	0.76

From the results in Table (4), there were apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable educational level.

Job Site

Calculations of arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable job site are shown in Table (5).

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable job site

Principle	Levels of job site	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
A commitment of management	Senior Management	32	3.85	0.38
	Middle Management	40	3.81	0.41
	Employee	134	3.82	0.45
	Total	206	3.82	0.43
Importance of customers and employees	Senior Management	32	3.93	0.59
	Middle Management	40	3.83	0.68
	Employee	134	3.87	0.70
	Total	206	3.87	0.67
Standing of facts	Senior Management	32	3.51	0.71
	Middle Management	40	3.67	0.78
	Employee	134	3.62	0.77
	Total	206	3.61	0.76
Full Participation	Senior Management	32	3.40	0.66
	Middle Management	40	3.50	0.70
	Employee	134	3.75	0.58
	Total	206	3.65	0.63
Continuous Improvement	Senior Management	32	4.07	0.67
	Middle Management	40	3.95	0.72
	Employee	134	3.87	0.78
	Total	206	3.91	0.76

From the results in Table (5), there were apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the study sample responses about the degree of applying the principles of total quality management according to the variable job site.

4.2 Conclusions

This study assessed the application of Total Quality Management (TQM) principles in Jordanian telecommunications companies, specifically Zain, Orange, and Umniah. The findings revealed a high approval rating for the management commitment variable (leadership) at 3.82, indicating a strong recognition of TQM's importance, despite noting some weaknesses in internal administrative policies. Furthermore, the importance placed on customers and employees received an average score of 3.87, reflecting the companies' focus on these stakeholders and emphasizing the need for employee empowerment in decision-making and customer service (Nzuve and Bakari, 2012). The Standing of Facts variable had an average approval of 3.64, suggesting that established laws and policies guide decision-making processes within these organizations.

Additionally, employee full participation scored 3.64, highlighting the companies' commitment to involving all employees in decision-making, aligning with findings from Al-Shamaila and Al-Nuwaisa (2020). Continuous Improvement emerged as the highest-ranked principle with a score of 3.92, underscoring a commitment to ongoing enhancements and research and development. Among management levels, senior

managers exhibited the highest relative importance index (RII) of 0.83, followed by middle management at 0.82. In contrast, employees had the lowest approval rating, with an RII of 0.80, indicating the least engagement among different tiers of management. These findings suggest that while TQM principles are being applied effectively within these companies, there is a critical need to address internal policy weaknesses and bolster employee engagement to enhance overall operational effectiveness and service quality.

4.3 Recommendations

4.3.1 Recommendations for Communication companies

Based on the findings of this study, which assessed the application of Total Quality Management (TQM) principles in the Jordanian telecommunications sector—specifically Zain, Orange, and Umniah—the following recommendations are proposed:

- *Promote a Culture of Quality:* Jordanian telecommunications companies should work to raise awareness about the culture of quality and embed its principles among employees, departments, and customers to create a collective quality culture. As the study findings indicate, achieving high scores in Management Commitment (3.82) and Customer Importance (3.87) reflects the necessity of cultivating a strong quality-oriented environment.
- *Support from Senior Management:* Senior management should ensure the provision of necessary resources for implementing TQM by establishing specific policies and plans to support quality programs. The findings emphasize management commitment as crucial, aligning with established research highlighting the importance of leadership in TQM effectiveness (Al-Majali et al., 2022).
- *Regular Partner Meetings:* Regular meetings should be organized with key stakeholders—clients, suppliers, and employees—to strengthen relationships and gather feedback on experiences and suggestions for improving services. The study revealed that both Employee Full Participation and Standing of Facts scored moderately (3.64), pointing to the need for enhanced stakeholder engagement.
- *Focus on Customer Relationships:* Companies should prioritize consolidating relationships with customers and actively listen to their feedback to enhance service quality. The principle of Continuous Improvement (KAIZEN), scoring the highest at 3.92, supports the emphasis on customer feedback as a route to refining service quality.
- *Continuous Employee Training:* Continuous training should be provided across all departments (upper, middle, and lower management) to establish TQM principles as a consistent operational policy within Jordanian telecommunications companies. This aligns with the finding that ongoing enhancements are essential for embedding TQM within the organizations.

4.3.2 Recommendations for Future Work

- **Expand Research Scope:** Future research should broaden the focus on TQM within the telecommunications sector specifically to explore additional dimensions and insights.
- **Conduct Comparative Studies:** Undertake comprehensive studies on TQM across other service sectors and compare the results with this research to facilitate further development.
- **Examine TQM Principles:** Investigate TQM principles as independent variables and their influence on service quality in the telecommunications sector as a dependent variable. Specific areas for future investigation could include: a) The impact of management commitment (leadership) on service quality in the Jordanian telecommunications sector. b) The effect of customer and employee importance on service quality in the Jordanian telecommunications sector. c) The influence of focusing on factual application on service quality. d) The impact of continuous improvements (KAIZEN) on service quality. e) The effect of full employee participation on service quality.

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